

Attenuation of Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Hepatorenal Damage by Methanol Extract of *Justicia carnea* Leaves in Male Wistar Rats

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Abstract

The liver and the kidney are two of the major organs affected by the complications of diabetes mellitus. This study was aimed at investigating the ameliorative effects of methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves (MEJC) on liver and kidney dysfunction in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic wistar rats. Thirty-six (36) male wistar rats weighing between 180 to 200 g (mean weight = 190 ± 10 g) were purchased and divided into six (6) groups, each with six (6) rats. Group 1 designated as the normal control, receiving water and standard rat chow only, group 2 was induced with diabetes and but untreated, while group 3 rats were induced with diabetes and treated with 50 mg/kg bw of metformin, groups 4, 5 and 6 were induced with diabetes and treated with 100, 200 and 500 mg/kg bw of MEJC, respectively. Diabetes mellitus was induced in the rats by intraperitoneal injection of 50 mg/kg bw of STZ. All the rats were provided with standard rat chow and unrestricted access to water for the period of the study. After 21 days of the treatment, the rats were sacrificed, and blood samples were collected for biochemical analysis, while the livers and kidneys were harvested and processed for histopathological screening. The acute toxicity study of the methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves shows no potential toxic effects. The results also showed that there were significant ($p < 0.05$) increases in ALP, AST and ALT in the diabetic control when compared to the normal control which significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced in the metformin treated group (group 3) and the groups given graded doses of the MEJC (groups 4-6). The hepatic and renal indices were significantly attenuated in the diabetic treated groups compared to the diabetic untreated groups. Albumin, direct bilirubin and total bilirubin concentrations were increased in the diabetic control group compared to the diabetic metformin and extract treated groups. There was significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) concentration of total protein in the diabetic untreated control group compared to the metformin and extract treated groups. Urea and creatinine levels of the diabetic control increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the normal control while the levels decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the metformin treated group and graded doses of the extract respectively. The histomorphology of the liver and kidney sections showed amelioration in the damaged cells to near normal architecture. From the results of this present study, the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves attenuated the hepatorenal damage caused by the STZ-induced diabetes in wistar rats and hence have both hepatoprotective and nephroprotective potentials.

Keywords: Attenuation, Diabetes mellitus, Hepatorenal damage, *Justicia carnea*, Streptozotocin

1.0 Introduction

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high blood glucose levels, resulting from insufficient endogenous insulin production by the pancreatic beta cells leading to type-1 diabetes or impaired insulin secretion and/or action leading to the type-2 diabetes. [1]. Type-1 diabetes is an autoimmune disease characterized by T-cell mediated destruction of the pancreatic beta cells due to a gradual

development of insulin resistance and beta cell dysfunction, which are strongly associated with obesity and a sedentary lifestyle[1]. The prevalence of diabetes is increasing worldwide, especially in developing countries. It has been estimated that there would be a 69% increase in the number of adults that would be affected by the diabetes between 2010 and 2030, compared to 20% for developed countries [2]. The discovery of medicinal plants containing bioactive

substances (phytochemicals and secondary metabolites) that have the potentials to shield humans from sicknesses, offer advantageous qualities for the treatment and prevention of a variety of illnesses [3,4]. Many synthetic drugs are available for the management of diabetes but the high cost of obtaining these drugs and the potential negative effects makes it necessary to search for the alternatives for the management and prevention of various ailments [5, 6]. The search for appropriate hypoglycemic agents has been focused on plants used in traditional medicine that may provide better treatments than currently used drugs [7]. Hepatotoxicity is the term used to describe liver damage or malfunction brought on by a xenobiotic or medication overdose [8]. It is a liver injury caused by chemicals that has the potential to harm the liver when taken excessively or sometimes even at the early exposure even at the recommended dosage. However, other chemical agents employed in factories and laboratories activities, natural chemicals (such microcystins), and herbal medicines can also lead to hepatotoxicity [9]. Numerous biological and environmental pollutants exposed to the body have been reported to potentially harm the liver and cause major health issues. According to Saukkonen et al. [10], hepatotoxicity can arise from various sources, such as the direct toxicity of the original chemical, a relative metabolite, or an immunologically mediated response affecting the hepatocytes, biliary epithelial cells and/or hepatic vasculature. Nephrotoxicity describes the detrimental impact on the kidneys, caused by a variety of chemicals, such as drugs, poisons, and other compounds. Depending on the degree and length of exposure, nephrotoxicity can result in either acute kidney damage or chronic kidney disease, affecting its physiological significance [11]. Diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is frequently associated with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus with the oxidative stress as a major factor responsible in the occurrence and progression of DKD.

Africa is rich with more than 5000 known medicinal plant species used for treatment and prevention of a wide variety of diseases [13]. Many of these plants are being evaluated for their phytochemical compositions, medicinal and therapeutic properties including antioxidant, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, antihypertensive, hepatoprotective and nephroprotective effects amongst others [14]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has sponsored scientists to conduct research for the evaluation of the potentials of natural products as alternative

medicine aimed to make a significant contribution to healthcare [15].

Justicia carnea is a flowering plant, widely distributed in various parts of Africa, including Nigeria. In the Eastern parts of Nigeria, it is referred to as "Ogwu Obara" where a decoction of the plant is used as blood tonic administered to anemic patients, pregnant women as well as women undergoing menstruation [16]. In addition to its traditional use as a hematinic, it is also used locally in the treatment and management of different ailments, such as diarrhea, arthritis, liver disease, diabetes, inflammation, gastrointestinal disorders and rheumatism [17, 18]. The plant has also been reported to possess antidiabetic, antioxidant, antiviral, hypocholesterolemic, and cardioprotective properties [14, 19, 20, 21]. This present work therefore aimed at investigating the ameliorative effects of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves on liver and kidney dysfunction in STZ-induced diabetes in wistar rats.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 Chemicals and Reagents

All the chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical grade and were products of either British Drug House (BDH) (England), or Sigma Aldrich Ltd. (USA)

2.2 Sample Collection and Identification

The plant sample, leaves of *Justicia carnea* were collected from a botanical park located along the Benin-Lagos expressway Ugbowo, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. A plant taxonomist, Dr. Akinnibosun Henry Adewale of the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, identified and verified the plant leaves. A voucher specimen (no. UBH-J386) was deposited in the herbarium of the Department for reference.

2.2.1 Preparation of Plant Sample

The plant sample was washed, air dried and pulverized using a motorized grinder. After that, the powdered sample was steeped in 80 % methanol for 72 hours, stirring the mixture occasionally with a stirring rod to ensure optimal extraction. A muslin cloth was used to filter the solution, and the filtrate was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator (Buchi, Germany) at 60°C. The moisture was then removed by freeze-drying, and the resulting *Justicia carnea* methanol extract was stored in the refrigerator at -4°C until required for use.

2.3 Experimental Rats

A total number of thirty-six (36) male Wistar rats (8 weeks old) weighing between 180g – 200g (mean weight = 190 ± 10) were used in this study. The rats were purchased from the animal house of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Benin city, Edo state, Nigeria. The rats were acclimatized to our laboratory environment for two weeks under healthy and hygienic metal cages under standard laboratory conditions: room temperature, 55 – 65 % humidity and 12-h light/12-h dark cycle. The rats were allowed free access to rat chow and clean drinking water ad libitum. All the experiments were carried out in accordance with the National Health's Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Rats (NIH Publication No. 85–23) revised 1996. All the experimental procedures and protocols used in this study were reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City Nigeria with an approval reference number (FLSRE-2023-018).

2.4 Experimental Design

After the period of acclimatization, The Wistar rats were randomized into 6 groups of 6 rats each. Group 1 was designated as the control group which received only food and water throughout the duration of the experiment. The rats in groups 2 to 6 were induced with diabetes following intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg bw). Group 2 represent the diabetic untreated group, group 3 was treated with Metformin (25 mg/kg bw), while groups 4, 5 and 6 were treated with 100 mg/kg bw, 200 mg/kg bw and 500 mg/kg bw of methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves, respectively. The treatments lasted for 21 days after which the rats were sacrificed after an overnight fast.

2.4.1 Toxicity Test

An acute toxicity test was conducted on the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves using the Lorke (1983) method [22]. In this two-phase study, a total of eighteen (18) rats were used; in phase 1, the rats were divided into 3 groups of 3 rats each. Each group received oral gavage dose of the methanol extracts at 10, 100, 1000 mg/kg body weight, respectively. The rats were observed for signs of toxicity 60 minutes after administration and were continuously monitored at intervals of 6 hours for 24 hours. The absence of mortality in phase I necessitated a second phase of toxicity test. In phase 2, three rats were allocated to separate groups, each group receiving

a single, high-dose oral gavage of the methanol extracts at 1500, 2500, and 5000 mg/kg body weight, respectively. The rats were observed for signs of toxicity within 24 hours, with extended monitoring for an additional 48 hours to assess for delayed mortality.

2.4.2 Induction of Diabetes and Administration of Extracts

A 50 mg/kg bw of Streptozotocin (STZ) was administered intraperitoneally to induce diabetes. Fasting blood glucose levels were checked after three days and the rats with fasting blood glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL were considered diabetic. The fasting blood glucose concentration was determined with the aid of ACCU-CHEK Advantage II Active glucometer and strips. The test strip was inserted into the glucometer; blood sample was collected from the tail of the rat by tail tipping using a surgical blade. The blood was dropped on the dextrostix reagent pad. This was inserted into a microprocessor digital blood glucometer and the readings were recorded in mg/dl. Prior to the induction of diabetes, the rats were subjected to an overnight fast. The next morning, the fasting blood glucose levels of the experimental rats were measured and recorded. The blood glucose level was subsequently recorded on weekly basis for 21 days. The methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* was orally administered to the rats daily for 21 days of the experiment and the weight of the rats were also recorded on a weekly basis.

2.5 Liver Function Tests

2.5.1 Determination of Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) and Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST)

Plasma activity of ALT and AST enzymes were measured based on the colourimetric method of Reitman and Frankel [23], using Randox diagnostic kit.

2.5.2 Determination of Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP)

Commercial kit obtained from QuimicaClinicaApplicada, Spain was used based on the phenolphthalein monophosphate method according to the recommendations of the Rec GSCC (DGKC), (1972) [24].

2.5.3 Determination of Albumin

Commercial kit obtained from QuimicaClinicaApplicada, Spain, based on a bromocresol green dye – binding procedure was used for the quantitative estimation of albumin in serum [25].

2.5.4 Determination of Total bilirubin and Direct bilirubin

This was done by employing the method of Jendrassik and Grof [26] using assay kit obtained from QuimicaClinicaApplicada, Spain.

2.5.5 Total Protein Determination

The concentration of total protein was determined by colorimetric method, which was described by Weichselbaum [27].

2.6 Lipid Profile Tests:

The HDL-cholesterol was determined based on the precipitation method of Wieland and Siedel [28] using Randox kit. Total cholesterol was estimated by an enzymatic method of Zoppi and Fellini [29] using Randox Kit, while triacylglycerol was determined by enzymatic procedure described by Trinder, [30] using Randox kit. The equation of Friedewald et al [31] was used to estimate the LDL cholesterol concentration. The method of Li et al [32] was used to determine the total cholesterol and the triglycerides level was evaluated using the method of Tietz et al [33]

2.7 Kidney Function Tests:

2.7.1 Determination of Creatinine

The procedure defined by Bartels and Bohmer [34] was used to evaluate creatinine concentration.

2.7.2 Determination of Urea

The system defined by Fawcett and Scott was used to estimate urea concentration [35].

2.7.3 Blood Electrolyte Test

Exactly 15 μ l of the plasma sample was aspirated by Ion Selective Electrode (ISE) and the results of Na^+ , K^+ , HCO_3^- and Cl^- were displayed on the screen of the automated electrolyte analyzer in mmol/L.

2.8 Histopathological study

At the end of the 21 days of treatment, the rats were sacrificed, and the organs of interest (liver and kidney) were harvested for histological studies. The organs were rinsed in normal saline, soaked in 10% formalin for 12 hours and prepared according to the paraffin wax embedding technique by staining with hematoxylin and eosin for microscopic

evaluation. Histopathological examination was carried out under a light microscope, examined, and photomicrographed (magnification x400). In each H&E section, exactly 25 circular tubules were measured in two axes drawn perpendicular to each other with the aid of an image analyzer (Image Proplus, version 3.0).

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (SEM). Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used to analyze the data using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The various treatment groups were compared using Duncan multiple range test. Statistical significance was assumed at $p < 0.05$.

3.0 Results

3.1 Acute toxicity Test of *Justicia carnea* Methanol Leaves Extract

During this study periods, the treated rats did not show any toxicity sign and symptoms at the highest dose of 5000 mg/kg bw and the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves did not produce any rat mortality both phase 1 and 2 acute toxicity test (Tables 1).

Table 1: Phase 1&2 Acute toxicity Test

Dose (mg/kg body weight) of methanol extract	Phase 1 mortality	Phase 2 mortality
10	0/3	-
100	0/3	-
1000	0/3	-
1500	-	0/3
2500	-	0/3
5000	-	0/3

3.2 Effect of Graded Doses of Methanol Extract of *J. Carnea* Leaves on Rat Body Weight

The impact of methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves on body weight changes in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats is presented in Table 2. There were increases in the body weights of the Wistar rats across the groups. Group 4 and 5 had a significantly lower weight gain when compared to the normal control and diabetic control.

Table 2: Changes in the Body Weight of Diabetic Rats Treated with *J. carnea* Extract

Groups	Initial Body Weight (g)	Final Body Weight (g)	Weight Loss/Gain (g)
Group 1 (Control)	109.53±3.13	192.80±14.34	83.28±14.49
Group 2 (Diabetic Control)	133.75±14.41	212.11±17.24	78.36±9.15
Group 3 (Metformin)	118.33±5.23	178.58±11.19	66.20±9.74 ^b
Group 4 (100mg of Extract)	118.36±12.64	176.67±18.24	58.31±9.52 ^{ab}
Group 5 (200mg of Extract)	112.04±4.43	153.99±5.54	41.95±1.45 ^{ab}
Group 6 (500mg of Extract)	125.81±6.59	211.08±15.88	85.27±9.29 ^b

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3). Values with superscript ^a are significantly different (p < 0.05) from the normal control group while values with superscript ^b are significantly different from the diabetic control group

3.2.1 Changes in the Organ Weight of Diabetic Rats Treated with *J. carnea* Extract

significantly increased weights of the liver and kidney in group 2 (the diabetic untreated group) when compared to the other groups.

The final weights of the liver and kidney is presented in table 3 below. There was a

Table 3 Changes in the Organ Weight of Diabetic Rats

Groups	Liver	Kidney
Group 1 (Control)	4.57±0.18 ^b	1.14±0.09
Group 2 (Diabetic Control)	8.04±0.58 ^a	1.43±0.18
Group 3 (Metformin)	4.44±0.28 ^b	0.77±0.11 ^{a,b}
Group 4 (100 mg/kg)	3.53±0.34 ^{a,b}	0.66±0.03 ^{a,b}
Group 5 (200 mg /kg)	3.78±0.09 ^b	0.67±0.04 ^{a,b}
Group 6 (500 mg/kg)	4.18±0.23 ^b	0.76±0.05 ^{a,b}

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3). ^a represent significant difference from normal control (p<0.05). ^b represents significant difference from diabetic control (p<0.05)

3.3 Effect of Methanol Extract of *J. carnea* Leaves (ME) on Fasting Blood Glucose Concentration in STZ-induced Diabetic Rats

administration of streptozotocin when compared to the normal control. Administration of the ME of *J. carnea* leaves reversed the STZ-induced hyperglycaemia in a dose-dependent response, comparable with metformin administration for 21 days post administration. The glucose level of the diabetic control significantly increased (p < 0.05) compared with the normal control and diabetic treated groups after the 21 days study period.

Table 4 reveals the influence of the methanol extract of *J. carnea* on fasting blood glucose levels in STZ-induced diabetic rats. The result indicates that the blood glucose level of the diabetic control and the ME-treated diabetic groups increased significantly (p < 0.05) three days after

Table 4: Effect of Methanol Extract of *J. carnea* Leaves on Fasting Blood Glucose Concentration (mg/dL) in STZ-induced Diabetic Rats

Group	Initial	Week			
		1	2	3	4
Group 1 (Control)	76.00±4.15	98.87±2.33 ^a	103.67±2.53 ^b	92.33±2.37 ^b	65.5±3.42 ^b
Group 2 (Diabetic Control)	94.67±14.45	305.00±27.40 ^a	475.00±41.02 ^a	368.00±54.08 ^a	369.33±28.01 ^{ab}
Group 3 (Metformin)	62.20±3.88	310.80±56.81 ^a	286.40±55.00 ^{ab}	204.60±51.17 ^{ab}	168.00±76.00 ^{ab}
Group 4 (100 mg/kg)	58.80±4.11	283.20±50.71 ^a	223.00±58.15 ^{ab}	222.00±59.05 ^{ab}	171.20±67.12 ^{ab}
Group 5 (200 mg /kg)	56.80±1.65	370.20±49.42 ^a	321.75±53.10 ^{ab}	295±112.15 ^{ab}	222.33±62.22 ^{ab}
Group 6 (500 mg/kg)	59.17±6.32	297.67±43.31 ^a	240.20±70.83 ^{ab}	190.00±55.08 ^{ab}	53.00±12.00 ^b

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n=3). Values with superscript "a" are significantly different from the normal control while values with superscript "b" are significantly different from the diabetic control (p<0.05). Values with superscripts 'a and b' are significantly different from both normal and diabetic controls (p<0.05) but not significantly different when compared to the Metformin treated groups.

3.4 Effect of methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* on hepatic indices in STZ-induced diabetes rat

The effects of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves on the activities of ALP, ALT and AST as well as the concentrations of total bilirubin, direct bilirubin, albumin and total protein is presented in table 5. There was a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the activities of ALP in groups 4 and 5 when compared to the normal control. The activity of ALP decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) when the normal control and group 6 was compared to the diabetic control. All the groups showed significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in the activity of ALT when compared to the diabetic control, while the normal control only showed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) with group 5 and the normal control. The AST concentration also increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the diabetic control when compared to the normal control and the treated groups. The diabetic control and group 5 showed significant

difference ($p < 0.05$) in the activity of ALT when compared to the normal control while the diabetic control group was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from group 3, 4 and the normal control. Total bilirubin decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in group 6 and normal control when compared to the diabetic control group but there was no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) when all other groups were compared to the diabetic control group for direct bilirubin. There was elevation in the direct bilirubin level when compared to the normal control but only the increase observed in group 4 and 5 were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Albumin decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in group 3, 5 and 6 when compared to the normal control but the difference was not statistically significant when compared to the diabetic control. Total protein increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) in all other groups when compared to the normal control but a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) was noticed when the normal control was compared to the diabetic control.

Table 5: Effect of methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* on hepatic indices in wistar rats

Parameters	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
ALP(IU/L)	0.035±0.01 ^b	0.168±0.04 ^a	0.121±0.122	0.219±0.06 ^a	0.214±0.04 ^a	0.054±0.01 ^b
ALT(IU/L)	275.16±3.59 ^b	357.27±3.34 ^a	272.69±1.11 ^b	281.59±4.84 ^b	255.99±8.03 ^{a,b}	276.35±4.77 ^b
AST(IU/L)	281.59±1.11 ^b	388.44±6.20 ^a	271.61±6.77 ^b	291.60±5.55 ^b	253.76±10.73 ^a	269.63±2.85
TB (µmol/L)	0.09±0.01 ^b	1.70±0.48 ^a	0.54±0.11	0.55±0.13	0.62±0.08	0.25±0.02 ^b
DB(µmol/L)	0.19±0.04	0.61±0.17	0.73±0.52	1.10±0.31 ^a	1.06±0.20 ^a	0.43±0.03
ALB (g/L)	3.07±0.18	2.61±0.25	2.19±0.24 ^a	2.34±0.27	1.89±0.37 ^a	1.95±0.21 ^a
TP (g/L)	3.96±0.68 ^b	6.26±0.51 ^a	6.46±0.15 ^a	5.83±0.16 ^a	5.82±0.34 ^a	5.40±0.16 ^a

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. (n=3). ^a represents significant difference from control ($p < 0.05$), while ^b represents significant difference from diabetic control ($p < 0.05$). TB = Total Bilirubin; DB = Direct Bilirubin; ALB = Albumin; TP = Total Protein

3.5 Effect of *Justicia carnea* extract on Renal indices of streptozotocin induced diabetes rat

The effects of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves on renal indices is presented in Table 6. When the Metformin and methanol extract treated, the groups were compared to the normal and diabetic control groups, and a non-significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed in the plasma electrolytes, potassium and chloride. The results show significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower sodium

levels between the normal control group, groups 2, 3, and 4. However, significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher sodium levels were between the group 5 and the normal control group compared with the diabetic control. The urea concentration of the normal and diabetic control groups did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) differ but a significant decrease was observed in the creatinine levels of the extract treated groups and the diabetic control.

Table 6: Effect of Methanol Extract of *Justicia carnea* Leaves on Renal Indices in STZ-Induced Diabetic Rats

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
Chloride (mmol/L)	93.30±0.55	93.57±8.31	98.48±5.03	91.78±3.92	99.82±6.94	91.51±3.25
Sodium (mmol/L)	140.61±3.97 ^b	124.24±4.49 ^a	130.42±1.19 ^a	130.91±1.31 ^a	135.15±4.28 ^b	131.76±0.32
Potassium (mmol/L)	3.91±0.11	4.23±0.29	4.32±0.31	4.75±0.23	4.14±0.25	3.8±0.07
Creatinine (µmol/L)	39.43±0.31	48.97±3.39	45.43±0.15	30.08±0.30	41.07±9.24	48.31±0.56
Urea(mmol/L)	3.21±0.03 ^b	4.18±0.01 ^a	3.15±0.03 ^b	3.22±0.06 ^b	3.19±0.02 ^b	3.49±0.03 ^{a,b}

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. (n=3). ^a represents significant difference from control ($P < 0.05$) while ^b represents significant difference from diabetic control ($p < 0.05$)

3.6 Effect of Methanol Extract of *Justicia carnea* on Lipid Profile of STZ-Induced Diabetic Rats

The effect of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves on the lipid profile is presented in table 7. There was increase in LDL cholesterol concentration in the diabetic untreated group when compared to the normal control but the increase was not statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Groups 3, 5 and 6 showed significant decreased in LDL cholesterol concentration when compared to the normal control and diabetic control. The HDL cholesterol increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) when the diabetic group was compared to the normal

control. The treated rats in groups 3, 5 and 6 also reduced significantly ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the normal control and diabetic control. Triglyceride level decreased significantly ($P < 0.05$) in the diabetic group when compared to the normal control and other groups. There was also a significant decrease ($P < 0.05$) when the treated groups were compared to the normal control. Total cholesterol level increase significantly ($P < 0.05$) in the diabetic untreated group when compared to the normal control and all other groups. The treated rats in group 5 and 6 also showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the normal control.

Table 7: Effect of Methanol Extract of *Justicia carnea* on Lipid Profile of STZ-Induced Diabetic Rats

Parameters	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
LDL	460.13±79.67	550.35±69	184.96±51.24 ^{a,b}	469.16±56.34	148.87±27.06 ^{a,b}	166.91±28.17 ^{a,b}
TRIG	2.87±0.02 ^b	2.58±0.16 ^a	2.37±0.02 ^{a,b}	2.32±0.01 ^{a,b}	2.34±0.03 ^{a,b}	2.30±0.01 ^{a,b}
HDL	207.97±47.65 ^b	344.57±30.17 ^a	83.59±13.37 ^{a,b}	212.04±14.70 ^b	67.28±7.06 ^{a,b}	75.44±7.35 ^{a,b}
T.CHOL	88.49±0.72 ^b	149.64±1.44 ^a	93.52±1.44 ^b	95.68±2.16 ^b	53.96±0.72 ^{a,b}	77.70±4.32 ^{a,b}

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. (n=3). ^a represent significant difference from control ($P < 0.05$). ^b represents significant difference from diabetic control ($p < 0.05$). LDL=Low density lipoprotein cholesterol; TRIG = Triglycerides; HDL = High density lipoprotein cholesterol; T.CHOL = Total cholesterol

3.7 Effects of methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves on liver and kidney ultrastructure following 21 days oral administration in STZ-induced diabetic rats.

The histopathological analyses of the liver and kidney of the diabetic rats treated with methanol extracts of the leaves of *J. carnea* are presented in Figures 1a-1f and 2a-2f, respectively.

Fig 1a. Rat liver. Control. Composed of normal architecture: hepatocytes. (HC), sinusoids (SI), bile duct (BD), portal vein (PV): H&E x 400

Fig 1b. Rat liver of diabetic control showing severe vascular ulceration (VU), congestion (VC), periportal infiltrates of inflammatory cells (PI): H&E x 400

Fig 1c. Rat liver induced for diabetes + Standard drug showing: hepatocytes (HC), portal vein (PV), bile ducts (BD), all normal: H&E x 400

Fig 1d. Rat liver induced + 100mg Extract showing: normal architecture: hepatocytes (HC), portal vein (PV), bile ducts (BD): H&E x 400

Fig 1e. Rat liver induced + 200mg Extract showing: periportal infiltrates of inflammatory cells (PI), focal portal vascular ulceration (VU), congestion (CO): H&E x 400

Fig 1f. Rat liver induced + 500mg Extract showing: mild periportal mobilization of lymphocytes (PL), vascular ulceration, congestion, microvesicular steatosis: H&E x 400

Fig 2a. Rat kidney. Control. Composed of normal architecture: interstitial space (IS), tubules (TU), glomeruli (GL): H&E x 400

Fig 2b. Rat kidney induced for diabetes: interstitial congestion, glomerular shrinkage (GS), focal (tubular necrosis (TN): H&E x 400

Fig 2c. Rat liver induced + Standard drug: tubules (TU), glomeruli (GL), all normal (H&E x 400).

Fig 2d. Rat kidney induced + 100mg extract: active interstitial congestion (IC), tubules, glomeruli (GL), all normal: H&E x 400

Fig 2e. Rat kidney induced + 200mg extract: focal tubular necrosis (TN), glomerulus (GL): H&E x 400

Fig 2f. Rat kidney induced + 500mg extract: focal tubular necrosis (TN), glomerulus (GL): H&E x 400

4. 0 Discussion

A persistently high blood glucose level is the hallmark of diabetes mellitus, a metabolic disease. Insulin resistance, insufficient production of insulin, or both may be the cause of diabetes mellitus.

The acute toxicity study of the methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves showed that it has no potential toxic effects because there was no lethality or observable behavioral changes in the experimental rats (Table 1). Toxicity tests carried out in the preliminary studies indicated that there was no significant modification in the general behavior of the rats up to 5000 mg/kg bw of the extract which is the maximum allowable dose by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Guideline 423 for the testing of chemicals [36]. No death or adverse reactions or mortalities were observed in the rats that were administered low to high doses of the aqueous extract after 48 hours of administration. Therefore, the LD₅₀ of the extract may be greater than 5000 mg/kg which was the highest dose administered for the acute toxicity test. This observation suggests a high tolerance and safety level of the aqueous extract. This can be attributed to the extract lacking toxic constituents that could trigger adverse reactions at the tested doses. It can also imply that the leaves are safe for human and animal consumption although there is no data yet on chronic toxicity tests. The present finding from the acute toxicity study corroborates with the findings of Onyeabo et al [16] who reported that the ethanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves showed no toxicity signs up to 5000 mg/kg. Similarly, Orjiakor [21] reported that aqueous extract of *J. carnea* leaves up to 5000 mg/kg showed no sign of toxicity and mortality. Ukpabi-Ugo et al [37] also reported that the methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves was not toxic up to 2000 mg/kg.

Streptozotocin-induced diabetes led to a significant reduction in body weight compared to control rats. However, treatment with the methanol extract of the leaves of *J. carnea* resulted in a dose-dependent increase in body weight, suggesting a beneficial effect on weight management in diabetic conditions.

One of the body's main organs, the liver oversees metabolism, detoxification, and protein synthesis. According to Adesokan and Akanji [38] the actions of different enzymes within the tissue can serve as "markers" for identifying the harmful impact of external substances ingested by the

body. Biomarker enzymes such as AST, ALT, and ALP show whether the liver is injured or has impaired function. The most common parameters used to assess liver function are ALT, AST and ALP activities [39]. AST is an enzyme found in the cytoplasm and mitochondria in different tissues, including the heart and skeletal muscles, liver, kidneys, pancreas and erythrocytes [40,41]. ALT is a liver-specific enzyme localized primarily in the cytosol of hepatocytes and is a sensitive marker of hepatocellular damage in comparison to the levels of AST. It can provide a quantitative assessment of the degree of tissue damage, especially the hepatobiliary and kidney tissues [42,43]. In the present study, diabetic untreated rats showed significantly higher serum levels of AST, ALT, and ALP compared to the normal control. This may be due to oxidative damage caused by the generation of destructive radicals, which can lead to liver injury [44]. The treatment with *Justicia carnea* leaf methanol extract significantly reduced ALP at 500 mg/kg bw (group 6) and 100 mg/kg bw (group 4). The stabilization of the hepatic membrane and hepatocyte regeneration may be the cause of the ability of *Justicia carnea* leaf methanol extract to attenuate the values of the hepatic indices which may indicate the hepatoprotective activity of *Justicia carnea* leaves [45]. The body gets rid of bilirubin, a naturally occurring anion created when hemoglobin breaks down, through the liver. When the hepatobiliary ducts are blocked or injured, the liver cells' ability to eliminate bilirubin is compromised, which results in elevated bilirubin levels. In this study, there was an elevated levels of both total and direct bilirubin levels in comparison to the normal control. This elevated bilirubin level may be the resultant effect of hepatobiliary duct injury caused by STZ. The elevated levels of bilirubin in the diabetic untreated group were attenuated in the diabetic treated groups especially the group that received 500 mg /kg bw of extract. The liver produces albumin in addition to other blood proteins. It is one of the plasma proteins that the liver makes and oversees moving various materials through the blood, including fatty acids, calcium, hormones, bile salt, and some medications. In this study, there was a decrease in albumin level in the diabetic untreated group compared to the normal control group. This may be the consequence of STZ-induced hepatotoxicity leading to impaired synthesis of insulin and other essential plasma proteins. When compared to the normal control group, the diabetic control group and the treated groups showed a substantial increase in albumin

concentration. The treated and diabetic control groups did not differ significantly from one another.

According to Orisakwe et al [46], the kidney's primary function is to maintain homeostasis by eliminating metabolic waste and controlling intracellular fluid volume, electrolyte composition, and acid-base balance. The electrolytes, sodium, potassium, and chloride ions as well as urea and creatinine, are among the renal indices for assessing the kidney status. In this study, the diabetic control group had higher concentrations of urea and creatinine than the normal control group, with the creatinine concentration increasing more dramatically. The effect of diabetes induced by STZ in the experimental rats may be the cause of this rise in urea and creatinine in the diabetic control. To break down waste products found in muscles through creatinine phosphate metabolism, the liver synthesizes creatinine. A renal malfunction or other impairment is the cause of the buildup of plasma creatinine. Conversely, urea is a byproduct of protein metabolism and should be eliminated through the urine. It could build up because of diabetes-related nephrotoxicity which keeps urea in the blood. The kidney maintains electrolytes including sodium ion (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), and chlorine (Cl⁻) at minimal concentrations in the body. At the distal tubules of the nephrons, the electrolytes move through renal absorption to reabsorb or excrete these ions. However, any xenobiotic-induced nephron defect would impede this function, resulting in the buildup of these electrolytes and uneven distribution. There was amelioration of the renal indices in the diabetic treated groups compared to the diabetic untreated group indicating the efficacy of the methanol extract of *J. carnea* against nephrotoxicity associated with diabetes.

Evaluation of lipids, such as TC, TG, HDL-C, LDL-C and VLDL can provide vital information on predisposition of the heart to atherosclerosis as well as other associated coronary heart diseases [47,48]. Our findings showed that there was no significant difference in the lipid profile parameters in the extract treated groups when compared with the control group. This suggests that the *J. carnea* leaves may not cause any form of obesity and heart disease at the dose administered for the duration of the study. Because of the insufficient glucose utilization, diabetes is known to cause hyperlipidemia, resulting to an excessive mobilization of fat from adipose tissues [49]. The body of diabetic persons uses other metabolites including proteins and fatty acids instead of

glucose as its primary fuel [50]. The findings of this study showed that the diabetic untreated group had significantly higher levels of total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol than the normal control group. Following 21 days of treatments with varying concentrations of the *J. carnea* leaves extract and standard medications (Metformin), there was a significant drop in the total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, and increase LDL cholesterol in the diabetic treated group, suggesting an antihyperlipidemic effect of the methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves.

The photomicrograph of the liver of group 1 rats (Fig.1a) showed normal hepatic histo-architecture. The liver parenchyma shows normal portal hepatic features with the central vein, sinusoids radiating from the central vein and the hepatocytes appearing normal. The hepatocytes are densely packed with normal cellular structure. However, there were structural alterations in the liver parenchyma of group 2 rats. These alterations, includes desquamated, dilated, and congested central vein, apoptosis of hepatocytes with aggregation of macrophages, which are in line with previous report [32][51]. The hepatocytes (HC), sinusoids (SI), bile duct (BD) and portal vein (PV) on the portal zone were all normal. The diabetic untreated group showed that there was dilatation of the blood vessels leading to thinning of the wall causing vascular ulceration (Fig.1b). This ulceration of the blood vessel known as vasculopathy is a complication of atherosclerosis induced by diabetes [33,52]. The liver of the diabetic group treated with Metformin (Fig.1c) showed a significant reversal of the vasculopathy induced by diabetes, the alteration and other complications because of diabetes were also ameliorated. This pattern of restoration of the liver's ultrastructure was also observed for group 4 rats which were diabetic rats treated with 100 mg/kg bw of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* (Fig.1d). The liver of the diabetic rats treated with 200 mg/kg bw of the extract also showed a reversal of some structural complications induced by diabetes. This observation is consistent with previous findings [34,53]. In this study, it was observed that the photomicrograph of the livers of diabetic rats treated with 100 mg/kg bw of the extract (Fig.1e) was more like the normal control when compared to the photomicrograph of the livers of diabetic rats treated with 200 mg/kg bw (Fig.1f). The recovery of hepatocytes (diabetic rats treated with 500 mg/kg bw) to normal of was less pronounced compared to group 4 rats treated with 200 mg/kg

bw of the extract due to the level of congestion and vascular ulceration in the liver. The doses have varying effects on the impact of diabetes on the liver and in comparing the effect of the various doses of the extract to the normal control and the drug (Metformin), the 100 mg/kg bw of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* was more effective in the amelioration of the effect of STZ – induced diabetes in the liver than 200 and 500 mg/kg bw of the extract. However, it has been reported by Ukpabi-Ugo et al [37] that both low (200 mg/kg) and high (800 mg/kg) doses of *Justicia carnea* extract was effective in ameliorating the effect of diabetes on the liver. Diabetic kidney disease is the leading cause of end-stage kidney disease [35,54]. It is considered a microvascular complication that occurs in both diabetes mellitus type 1 and diabetes mellitus type 2. Thirty to forty percent of patients with diabetes mellitus develop diabetic nephropathy [36,55].

The photomicrograph of the kidney of the normal control group showed normal architecture of interstitial spaces, tubules and glomeruli (Fig.2a). The untreated group showed congestion of the interstitial space, shrinkage of the glomeruli and tubular necrosis (Fig.2b) which are some of the features of diabetic nephropathy caused by diabetes [36,38,55,56]. When the diabetic rats were treated with Metformin, the photomicrograph of their kidneys (Fig.2c) were similar to that of the normal control which is an indication of the effectiveness of metformin in the treatment of the effect of diabetes on the kidneys. The photomicrograph of diabetic rats treated with 100 mg/kg bw of the extract (Fig.2d) showed normal glomeruli, tubules and the interstitial spaces, were normal in comparison with the normal control, suggesting the effectiveness of the dose in the amelioration of the effect of diabetes on the kidney just like the standard drug, metformin. The photomicrographs of the kidneys of diabetic rats treated with 200 and 500 mg/kg bw of the extract respectively (Fig.2e and fig.2f), showed no shrinkage of the glomeruli compared to the diabetic control (Fig.2b) but focal necrosis was observed. From the histomorphology of the kidneys of diabetic rats treated with 100, 200 and 500 mg/kg bw of the extract, the various doses of the extract were effective in the attenuation of the diabetes-induced nephrotoxicity. This finding also aligns with the findings of Ukpabi-Ugo et al[36] who reported a restoration of the normal general structure of the kidney and the normal appearance of glomeruli and tubules after treatment of diabetic rats with *Justicia carnea* extract.

5.0 Conclusion

This study demonstrated the significant therapeutic potential of the methanol extract of *Justicia carnea* leaves in the treatment of diabetes mellitus and its resulting liver and kidney complications.

The results revealed the effectiveness of *J. carnea* leaves in lowering the blood glucose level due to its antihyperglycemic effect.

Streptozotocin-induced diabetes led to a significant increase in body weight compared to the control rats. However, the results show that treatment of body weight with the methanol leaves extract of *J. carnea* resulted in a dose-dependent modulation can a beneficial effect in weight management in diabetic conditions.

The methanol extract of *J. carnea* leaves was also able to attenuate the hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity associated with STZ-induced diabetics in wistar rats.

These findings underscore the medicinal properties of *Justicia carnea* and support its potential as a candidate for antidiabetic drug or adjuvant drug with other antidiabetic drugs. Further research and clinical trials are warranted to fully explore its potential, establish standardized dosing regimens for therapeutic applications and determine the mechanism of action of the leave extract. The liver and kidney histopathology results further demonstrated that low dosages of the extract (100 mg/kg bw) were more successful in ameliorating the damages induced by diabetes in the different organs. It is clear from the study's varied findings that *Justicia carnea* has several therapeutic benefits and can be utilized to manage diabetes mellitus.

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7.0 Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest related to the publication of this paper

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